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ANESTHESIA EFFECTS ON THE MANAGED *BOMBUS TERRESTRIS*
TERRESTRIS: A PROPEDEUTIC INVESTIGATION
TO STUDY THE CLIMATIC “REFUGEE” *BOMBUS KONRADINI*

Effetti dell'anestesia sulle colonie gestite di Bombus terrestris terrestris:
un'indagine propedeutica allo studio del “rifugiato” climatico Bombus konradini

Bombus konradini is a newly recognized bumblebee species found in high-altitude habitats of the Central Appennines (RICCIARDELLI D'ALBORE & PIATTI, 2003; MARTINET *et al.*, 2018). The species is currently listed as Endangered in the Red List of the Italian threatened bees, according to which the main obstacles to its survival are posed by climate change and habitat degradation (RASMONT *et al.*, 2015; QUARANTA *et al.*, 2018). Despite being subject to such threats, and thus in need of immediate conservation measures, many aspects of *B. konradini*'s biology, ethology and distribution are still poorly known. Because of this, further research on the species is needed, as much as on low-impact manipulation methods and techniques that can be applied on the field, in order to study the species in its natural habitat, without posing a new problem to its populations. A first approach to the study of *B. konradini* could include finding newly emerged gynes and following their activity, leading to their nests and colonies, and subsequently observing colony life.

Marking is of great importance for following individuals of those species that cannot be easily and rapidly distinguished otherwise, like bumblebee ones. Different techniques applied to field work on bumblebees are already supported by a number of studies illustrating several methods for capturing, marking, and manipulating in general, and many of them resort to anesthesia to simplify the procedures described (MARTIN *et al.*, 2006; OSBORNE *et al.*, 2008; POISSONNIER *et al.*, 2015). The most commonly used ways to induce a

narcotic state in bumblebees involve cold and carbon dioxide, with the latter being the most practical one during field sessions. However, despite anesthesia has proven to be a very useful tool, it is also known to have a plethora of side effects on treated subjects, ranging from anomalies in behaviours regarding brood care (POMEROY & PLOWRIGHT, 1979) to potential short and long-term memory losses (NICOLAS & SILLANS, 1989; STEC & KUSZEWSKA, 2020).

The aim of this investigation is to outline whether or not CO₂ anesthesia has negative effects on the survival of treated individuals of a managed, commercial bumblebee species, *Bombus terrestris terrestris*, under the assumption that such effects would be similar in the congeneric *B. konradini*. Two treatments, one including marking with CO₂ anesthesia and one marking without it, were applied by following the mark-recapture framework to three different *B. terrestris terrestris* colonies, used as replicates, all obtained from Bromotirrena s.r.l. One of the three colonies had to be excluded from the experiment, due to colony failure caused by Deformed wing virus (DWV) and probably *Nosema bombi*.

After a five-days stasis to allow the colonies to acclimatize to the new environment, 56 individuals in each of the two remaining nests were caught and marked via the application of coloured and numbered tags, typically used in beekeeping to mark queens; among these 56, 28 were anesthetized and 28 were not. Two days after the end of the marking session, recapture via video-recording took place, followed by video analysis. Of the total 112 individuals treated, 68 still marked ones were recaptured, and at least 7 presented clear signs of having removed their tag.

The number of marked and recaptured bumblebees was processed by χ^2 test, to assess potential negative effects of CO₂ anesthesia. Results obtained suggest that there is a significant association between the type of treatment used and the possibility of recapture ($\chi^2 = 7.337$, d f = 1, p = 0.007, $\alpha = 0.05$), indicating that CO₂ anesthesia somehow influences treated subjects, possibly compromising their survival.

Further experiments are needed to establish the nature of the effects that CO₂ anesthesia has on bumblebees' survival and activity, for example by considering subjects' weight, and also by focusing specifically on repercussions on memory in a homing experiment setting. Such experiments might even shed light on alternative administration techniques that may have lesser impact on treated individuals.

As of now, results advice against the use of CO₂ anesthesia on species at risk like *B. konradini*.

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